

ODYSSEUS

NEWSLETTER

3 r d I s s u e

THIRD NEWSLETTER

JULY 2024

In our third edition of ODYSSEUS Newsletter, the highlights of the project's progress for the past six months are featured. Find out where ODYSSEUS partners participated and what were the outcomes.

Find out about the project journey and core goals
<https://odysseusproject.eu/>

[@odysseus_heu](https://twitter.com/odysseus_heu)

[@odysseusproject-heu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/odysseusproject-heu)

Stakeholder Community!

Come aboard and help shape the future of border control by collaborating and sharing your insights with us! As a stakeholder, you'll be invited to participate in project events such as conferences, workshops, webinars, and internal meetings.

Stakeholder Community Registration Form

Completing the registration, you consent to Odysseus storing your personal data for the duration of the project. The Odysseus project is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy.

*** Required**

First name *	Last Name *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Name of Organisation *	
<input type="text"/>	
Website *	Email address *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Type of Organisation *	Country *
<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Why do you want to join the Odysseus Stakeholder Community? *	
<input type="text"/>	

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The 3rd ODYSSEUS Plenary meeting

On January 26, 2024, the 3rd Plenary meeting of **ODYSSEUS** took place online, marking a significant milestone in the collaborative efforts of the project's diverse team. The event provided a platform for partners to share their accomplishments from the past six months, outlining progress and achievements while setting the stage for the next phase of the project.

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The 1st Review meeting

On February 22, 2024, the 1st review meeting of the **ODYSSEUS** project was completed successfully. The project's progress, impact, and compliance has been evaluated by the Project Officers. It was an insightful session that delved deep into the **ODYSSEUS** journey, showcasing partners adherence to milestones and deliverables. Beyond celebrating **ODYSSEUS** achievements, areas for enhancement have been identified as well as strategies to mitigate potential risks. .

**1st Review
Meeting**

Progress Evaluation

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ODYSSEUS project at the 10th meeting of the DG MOVE Working Party on Rail Security (RAILSEC)

On February 1st, 2024, **ODYSSEUS** project was presented by the *UIC* Security Division in the pivotal 10th Working Party on Rail Security (RAILSEC) meeting at the European Commission Directorate-General Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE) headquarters in Brussels.

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ODYSSEUS

at the FCT and BM Synergy Workshop

ODYSSEUS participated at the FCT and BM Synergy Workshop on March 12, 2024, alongside TENSOR, FLEXI-Cross, and EITHOS projects. This virtual event explored the intricate interplay between Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT) and Border Management (BM) Horizon calls.

SIMAVI presented in-depth overview of the **ODYSSEUS** project. *VISB* highlighted technological milestones, emphasising AI integration for seamless EU border crossings by land, water, and rail. *ISIG* illuminated the ethical framework, ensuring **ODYSSEUS** alignment with EU principles and emerging AI regulations.

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ODYSSEUS

at STS-MigTec Network Annual Workshop

On April 9th, 2024, the **ODYSSEUS** project was presented at the STS-MigTec Annual Workshop, hosted by Utrecht University in the Netherlands. In the event, themed “Data Matters in Migration and Border Control,” the UIC Security Division presented a work-in-progress paper titled “Railway security checks at the border: between intrusive security technologies and fundamental traveller rights” .

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ODYSSEUS

at the First Automation & Robotics Expo in Greece

ODYSSEUS, represented by *ACCELIGENCE* and *SQUAREDEV*, made a notable impact at the first Automation and Robotics Expo in Greece at the Athens Metropolitan Expo Centre on April 12–14, 2024. The project’s commitment to pushing the boundaries of technology and addressing border control challenges with the use of innovative technologies was strongly emphasised.

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ODYSSEUS

at the 1st International Conference on the Security of the Blue Economy

ODYSSEUS was presented by *TELESTO* at the 1st International Conference on the Security of the Blue Economy (#SEC4BLUEconomy24) convened in Athens on April 23, 2024. The event shed light at the importance of security in the Blue Economy. **ODYSSEUS** addresses various security challenges faced by the water borders providing robust strategies and the means to mitigate risks and ensure the safety of critical maritime infrastructure.

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The 4th Plenary Meeting of the ODYSSEUS

The 4th Plenary Meeting of the **ODYSSEUS** Project Consortium in Athens on 23rd and 24th of May was a resounding success. Marked by constructive discussions, strategic planning, and a reaffirmed commitment to the project's goals. The event not only highlighted the progress made but also laid a strong foundation for future endeavors.

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ODYSSEUS

at BorderUAS final conference

ODYSSEUS On May 30, 2024, participated at the final conference of the BorderUAS project. The project, represented by *SIMAVI*, established synergy with BorderUAS at the beginning of the year. Both projects share a common goal of enhancing the security of Europe's external borders. As a sister project, ODYSSEUS will build upon the experiences shared by the BorderUAS Consortium.

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ODYSSEUS at the 5th International Conference in Electronic Engineering, Information Technology & Education (EEITE'2024)

The 5th International Conference in Electronic Engineering, Information Technology & Education (EEITE'2024) took place in Chania, Crete, Greece on May 31, 2024. *QUADIBLE* gave an informative paper presentation at the conference with the title “Seamless Identity Verification at Water and Land Borders.” This presentation highlighted the innovative approaches of **ODYSSEUS** that transform the way borders are controlled for people, cars, and goods.

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CONSORTIUM

STAY TUNED FOR UPCOMING ACTIVITIES, EVENTS, AND OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE WITH THE PROJECT!

